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INTELLIGENCE AND ITS THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

ANNOTATION

The article describes the intellect and its theoretical foundations, scientific research conducted by scientists and their opinions.

Keywords: intellect, mind, mind, thought, reflection, consciousness, scientific, research, theoretical, thinking, worldview.

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INTELLEKT VA UNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada intellekt va uning nazariy asoslari olimlar tomonidan olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari va ularning fikrlari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: intellekt, aql, zehn, fikr, muloxaza, ong, ilmiy, tadqiqot, nazariy, fikrlash, dunyoqarash.

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ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И ЕГО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье описывается интеллект и его теоретические основы, научные исследования, проводимые учеными, и их мнения.

Ключевые слова: интеллект, ум, разум, мысль, отражение, сознание, научный, исследовательский, теоретический, мышление, мировоззрение.

D. Veksler, G. Eysenck, L. Termen, R. Stenberg and others consider intelligence and creativity to be the unity of high-level human abilities. Intelligence is the highest level of creativity. This means not only that they are united, but that creativity is a derivative of intelligence. A high level of intelligence is the basis of a high level of ability. Lower intelligence - creates a lower level of intelligence. Hans Eysenck believed that creativity is a special manifestation of ability.

Creativity is characterized by high intelligence. Intelligence is the adaptation of humans and animals to new environments. V. Shterni, J. Piaget, D. Wexler and other authors also considered intelligence as a general ability that adapts people to new life conditions. In their research, they studied thousands of American schoolchildren using the logit method. In the process of research, their IQ (intelligence quotient) was determined at first. Pupils were divided into groups based on IQ coefficient and observed in 30, 40, 50, 60 years. Over the years, test takers with a high IQ have shown high performance in life and work.

Test takers with a lower IQ scored 30 times less than them. But other studies have shown that intelligence and creativity are not related to each other. Creativity is not adapting a person to life, but changing it. There are also theories that believe that the main factor of creativity is the disadaptation of a person, that is, his inability to adapt to the environment and social environment. Some scientists defined the creativity of a person as isolation from the outside world and people [1, P.47].

It is precisely when a person who has maladjustment to the real world, who cannot adapt, starts to create and create something new in order to overcome his loneliness. According to A. Adler, creativity in a person is a means of filling the complex of inaccuracies that exists in him. Empirical research shows that children with creative abilities face serious problems in the personal and emotional sphere. In studies, we can observe that the results achieved by such children at school are below their potential. D.J. is another scientist who opposes creativity and intelligence. Being Guilford, he builds his theory on the basis of two different ways of thinking. That is, convergent and divergent thinking. Convergent thinking is an analysis of all available means of solving a problem and choosing the only optimal one. Convergent thinking is built on intelligence [2, P.90].

Divergent thinking is a type of thinking that involves creating different options for solving a problem. Divergent thinking is based on creativity. Therefore, intelligence and creativity are two different abilities in general, which can be associated with the process of processing information. Creativity is responsible for the reproduction of existing information and the creation of an endless new model of it. Intelligence is responsible for applying that information in real practice and adapting to the environment. The owners of the third point of view see intelligence and creativity as two different factors that are inextricably linked. A. Maslau and others did not recognize creative ability.

Creative activity forms some personal characteristics (interest, risk-taking) in a person compared to ability. But for the manifestation of this activity, a person must have a high level of intellectual ability. According to them, a person with low intelligence will not have any creativity. People with average intelligence have average creativity, and people with an IQ of more than 120 have excellent creativity.

Let's analyze the relationship between intelligence and creativity from the point of view of evolution. We tend to think of intelligence as a fixed, adaptive capacity that does not produce great discoveries. Only return is characteristic of the intellect. According to psychologists, this idea is wrong. The reason is that in the theory of evolutionary development, the main factor of human anthropogenesis is the development of the intellect. An example of this is mastering fire and making weapons. Separating intelligence from creativity, personal creativity, originality, etc. are being adapted to creativity. [3, P.78].

Who was the first to create a great discovery, arrows, who thought of the possibility of taming fire? Intelligence? or Creativity? If there is creativity, then where did the intellect go? Therefore, such considerations reduce the role of intelligence in the creation of technical and scientific achievements of mankind. According to Spearman, humans have a general intelligence. In his opinion, people have their own abilities that separate them from each other.

Spearman developed factor analysis, a statistical procedure. He explained the temporal connections of related elements. According to Spearman, the total sum of competence depends on our mental attitude. To this day, Spearman's theory of general intelligence, that is, the theory of one-sided assessment of intelligence, has caused many protests. Unlike Spearman, Thurstone introduced assessment of mental abilities through 56 different tests, 7 clusters.

Thurstone did not judge people using a single scale. He believed that if a person successfully solves all the problems in 7 clusters, he will achieve the same success in all other areas. They compared mental ability with physical ability. In his opinion, the world champion in weightlifting can also practice figure sports. Because his physical training allows it. Satoshi Kanazawa (2004) sees general intelligence as a type of intelligence. General intelligence helps us solve problems in everyday life. By the 1980s, there was a comparison of Spiremennig's theory of single intelligence and Thurstone's theories of academic abilities.

According to them, if a person achieves success in one cognitive area, then he will achieve similar victories in other areas. The main factor in adaptation to life is not the general intelligence of a person, but the ability to interact with each other over time. H. Gardner considered intelligence as a sum of several abilities [4, P.24].

He conducted his research on people with low abilities. He believed that brain damage can disable one ability but leave the rest intact. Gardner conducted his research on subjects with physiological damage to some parts of the brain. They often have lower scores on intelligence tests. Some of the representatives of this syndrome have not developed speech. But they had the ability to calculate addition and subtraction as quickly as an electronic calculator. Some of them knew by heart the dates associated with a historical day.

Owners of this syndrome were able to achieve success even in artistic creation. Using the above facts, Gardner came to the idea that a person has several different minds rather than intelligence. In general, he says that a person has 8 different types of abilities. It has been said that if a person succeeds in one area, then he will also achieve good results in other areas. R. Shtenbegr, R. Wagner agreed with Gardner's idea, but they analyzed the presence of 3 different factors of intelligence in a person: The presence of akademic skills in solving problems. Such skills are assessed by determining the only correct answer in mental tests.

Practical intelligence helps to choose the most convenient solution to problems in everyday life in order to adapt to the environment. Creative mind. Representatives of this type are distinguished by their reaction in unfamiliar situations. The problem of creativity, which is a higher form of independent thinking, has been studied very deeply in foreign psychology, which is mainly interpreted as the creativity of ability.

The reason we do not use this definition as "creative" ("create" means "to create"), we used the term "creativity" to avoid the impression that creativity is a high level of intellectual activity. The problem of creativity in psychology has been consistently studied since the 1950s. But in our research, we tentatively called the term "creativity" in Uzbek as "mental creativity" and found it necessary to study it as a psychological basis of independent thinking. Thus, from now on, when thinking about mental creativity, non-standard thinking, its independence and "creativity" are meant.

The separation of creativity was motivated by the fact that there is no connection between traditional tests of intelligence and the success of problem solving. This quality essentially means that it depends on the ability to use the information given by the mind, the quick method and various methods in solving the tasks. In 1962, J. W. Getzels and P. W. Jackson published information in the press that there is no correlation between indicators of mental creativity [10, P.67].

They just entered their (Sr) coefficient to measure creativity. Mental talent is measured by the amount of success achieved in relation to the child's age in the child's certificate, and is determined by the IQ coefficient. Separation of IQ and Cr coefficients was a factor in contrasting ability and logic with mental creativity. For the same reason, by the 60s of the 20th century, more than 60 definitions of creativity were developed.

By analyzing the definitions of creativity, they can be divided into 6 types: gestalt definition (the creative process is defined as breaking existing gestalts and creating a better one), innovative (new) definition (according to the novelty of the final result oriented to the evaluation of creativity), aesthetic or expressive (emphasizing the self-expression of the creator), psychoanalytic (creativity is defined as the interaction between "He", "I" and "Ideal - I" 'reefing'); problematic (which defines creativity as a problem-solving process).

It can also incorporate J.P. Guilford's definition that "Creativity is a process of divergent abilities"), the sixth type can include various definitions that do not belong to any of the above-described types (for example, "replenishing the stock of "universal" knowledge) It is difficult to assess the content, essence and structure of the definitions related to the term of creativity collected in the present period.

Researchers say that "understanding what creativity is requires creative action. One of the authors of recent studies defines creativity as the achievement of something significant and new, that is, "in other words, the efforts of people to change the world." M.Wallach, one of the prominent researchers of creativity in the 60s of the 20th century, stated that intellectual tests are not correlated with creative achievements at high rates [10, P.35].

Due to the different development of intelligence and creativity among 11-12-year-old students, he divides them into 4 different groups: students who have reached a high level of intelligence and creativity evaluate themselves correctly, they have high self-control, they are interested in all new things and have independence in evaluation;

- students with a high intellectual level and a low level of creativity strive for success in school, but hide their secrets from others, and underestimate themselves;
- students with a low intellectual level and a high level of creativity are distinguished from others by their anxiety, inattention, and lower social adjustment;
- students with a lower intellectual level and creativity index easily adapt to the situation, high social intellectual level, but weak subjects evaluate themselves correctly.

Thus, the relationship between the creative process and the level of intelligence affects the personal characteristics of students and their adaptation methods. According to Stenberg and Gardner, several abilities can make a person lucky.

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